

OVERCOMING CHILDREN'S EXPRESSIVE ALALIA AT THE BEGINNING OF LOGOPEDIC THERAPY

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Abstract. *Currently, the number of children in need of correctional assistance is increasing in many countries of the world. According to the World Health Organization, speech disorders of various degrees are currently observed in an average of 30% of children admitted to the first grade, that is, when viewed objectively, during the preschool period, speech functions do not develop at the standard level in one third of the children's population and require additional corrective action from specialists. On the contrary, it is determined that phonetic-phonemic defects of speech (disorders in the pronunciation of sounds) appear in 15-25 per cent of the general population of children. According to the US National Centre for Health Statistics, voice disorders (articulatory or phonological disorders) in preschool children are 8-9 per cent. 5 per cent of children admitted to the first grade have speech defects such as speech disorders, stuttering, and dysarthria.*

Keywords: *expressive alalia; dialogue; communicative situation; grammatical model; grammatical forms; phrasal structures; stages of formation.*

Expressive alalia is one of the most severe and persistent forms of speech pathology of speech pathology. Many children with alalia do not acquire language and remain with little or no speech even by the time they enter school.

The complex symptom complex of linguistic and non-linguistic disorders inherent in this pathology has a negative impact not only on speech communication, but to a certain extent also on the development of cognitive activity, the development of certain aspects of personality, and often hinders the achievement of needs and aspirations significant for the emerging personality.

Alalia is characterized by the violation of all subsystems of language: syntactic, morphological, lexical and phonemic. Typical manifestations of alalia area grammatisms, disorders of actualization words, difficulties in selecting and combining phonemes, violations of the syllabic structure of words. The most important criteria for determining expressive alalia are the following:

- 1) a delay in the rate of normal language acquisition;
- 2) pathological development of language;
- 3) preservation of hearing;
- 4) satisfactory understanding of age-appropriate addressed speech.

In this article an attempt is made toto present a system of speech therapy work at the initial stage of overcoming expressive alalia expressive alalia. At the origins of the proposed system are the ideas of such outstanding researchers of alalia, such as B.M. Grinshpun and V.A. Kovshikov It is known that language is formed as holistic formation. "For this purpose in speech therapy work it is advisable to use a concentric system of material distribution, where each concentration includes a gradually becoming more complex totality of all subsystems of language (lexical, syntactic, morphological and phonemic) The main vector of correction We determine the main vector of correctional influence based on the pro-Overcoming expressive alalia in children at the

initial stage of speech therapy work Volga Pedagogical Bulletin of the regularities of language formation in ontogenesis. The child in the process of language acquisition language goes from content to form, from general to particular, from simple to complex, from predicative semantic structures to nominative, from contrasting forms to their shades, from the dialogic form of speech to the monologic form. Following B.M. Grinshpun, we suggest that speech therapy work should be oriented towards the creation of such "key links" in children, which caused the development of their speech links", which condition the formation of the language system as a whole. To these links B.M. Grinshpun attributes development of the predicative function and the formation of elements of grammatical structure. Language and speech are formed only in communication. Therefore, the main technique speech therapy work is the construction of dialogue in the appropriate communicative situation. We propose to build speech therapy work to overcome alalia based on the traditional stages accepted in speech therapy:

- Stage 1 - preparatory, its goal is to form an understanding of the grammatical meanings of words in impression speech

- Stage 2 - the main stage, its goal is to form primary language skills in expressive speech. The content of this stage is the formation of skills to express grammatical meaning in the appropriate grammatical form of words, to use grammatical forms of words correctly, to differentiate close grammatical forms of words. In contrast to the generally accepted approach, we propose to carry out the formation of communicative skills simultaneously with the above-mentioned stages. This approach, as it seems to us, will allow us to realize the activity principle in the process of language formation. The main stage, in its turn, consists of three sub-stages let's formulate the tasks facing the speech therapist at the first sub-stage:

1. To teach to use in independent expressive speech a one-joint one-word sentence, represented by a verb in the form of the indicative inflection, present tense, singular, 1st person with the ending inclination, present tense, singular, 1st person with the ending -u(y).

2. To teach to use in independent expressive speech a one-word sentence presented by a verb in the form of the present tense, singular, 1st person with the ending -u(yu).one-word sentence, represented by verb in the form of the imperative mood, present tense, singular number, 2nd person with a zero suffix and the suffix -Let us dwell on the description of the technology of speech therapy work. The speech therapist, using the "maternal method", creates a communicative situation, denoting it with the appropriate grammatical model. For example, an adult encourages the child to perform a joint action: "Go!", and then accompanies this action with a verbal response "I'm coming". In this way, the unity of motor and verbal reactions is achieved (B.M. Grinshpun), a connection is established between linguistic meaning and linguistic form. In the process of joint activity, the teacher, addressing the pupil, initiates a unidirectional dialogue:

- What are you doing?
- Idý.
- Kachý.
- Pull.
- Holdý.
- Sitting.
- Berý.

We need to pay attention to selection of linguistic material. Grammatical models used at this stage should be frequent, accessible in semantics and form, and serve the needs of the child.

At the initial stages of work it is necessary to use the most productive forms of word modification, the endings of which have a "perceptual convexity". A.M. Gorchakova, E.A. Chaladze 28 Volga Pedagogical Bulletin. convexity" (D. Slobin) that is in a strong striking position. Attention should be paid to the wording of the questions, which aim to elicit a verbal response from the child. We suggest the following sequence of using such questions:

1. A question containing the name action: "Are you coming?"
2. Negative technique question:
"Are you standing (while the child performs the opposite action)?"
"What are you doing?"
3. Alternative question: "Are you walking or standing?"
4. General question: "What are you doing?"

Next, the teacher organizes a communicative situation through a dialogue directed at the interlocutor: "Tell Petya: 'Sit down!'" or "Tell Petya to sit down!" In this case, the grammatical model is worked out - a sentence consisting of a predicate, expressed by a verb in the form of the imperative mood, present tense, singular, 2nd person zero suffix and suffix -i. Let us formulate the tasks facing the speech therapist at the second sub-stage of the main stage:

1. To teach to use in independent expressive speech one-joint two-word sentence (predicate + object).

2. Teach to use in independent expressive speech the verb in the form of the indicative mood, present tense, singular, 1st person.

3. To teach to use in independent expressive speech a noun (animate/inanimate, 1st declension, singular, accusative case). Let us consider the content of the second sub-stage. Corrective and speech therapy work is based on one-word sentences worked out earlier. The center of the sentences remains the predicate, expressed by a verb in the form of either the 1st person present tense or the accusative case. 1st person present tense or the imperative mood. It should be remembered that speech communication is formed in the activity, and not in the process of mechanical repetition of individual words. Object-practical, play and other types of children's activities are in themselves a developing means. They make correctional lessons interesting and useful both for cognitive and speech development of children. The speech therapist specially organizes activities (drawing, modelling, washing, cleaning, etc.) of the child. At this stage are important didactic games such as "Let's do together", "Repeat after me". In the process of activity, the adult addresses a question to the child, and the child joins the conversation, using a one-word sentence in response. The speech therapist asks questions with the support of on objects and pictures, in the name of which there is an accented ending. When evaluating the child's answers should pay attention to the correctness of pronunciation attention to the correct pronunciation ending (sový). Later they use words with a stressless ending (Tányu). At this stage is of great importance is the timely assistance of a speech therapist to the child in establishing speech communication. This assistance can be of different nature, for example: setting a feasible speech task before the children, combining speech activity with various forms of productive activity. speech activity with various forms of productive activity (games, labour, drawing, modelling, etc.), various variants of rewards for correctly constructed phrase. When mastering the lexical structure language of the child should pay attention to the available lexical meaning, the most frequently used words. You can offer the following lexical minimum:

- Who are you holding?

- Owl. (Fox. Goat. Osý. Sheep.)
- Mama. (Papa. Vova. Katya.)
- What are you carrying?
- Vata. (Mya tu. Tanya.)

The following communicative situations

- Who (what) are you molding?
- Who (what) are you washing?
- Who (what) do you draw?
- Who (what) are you treating?
- Who (what) do you teach?
- Who (what) do you carry?
- Whom (what) do you iron?
- Whom (what) do you sell?
- Whom (what) do you hide?
- Who (what) are you holding?

The speech therapist needs to use the most important, communicatively significant language units. A good learning effect is given by the technique of working with a personal photo album. A family photo is used. The child is offered to look at it. In a relaxed form they ask the question "Who do you see? do you love? Who are you hugging? Who Who do you kiss?" Expect to get an answer: "Mama. (Papa. Bab. Deda. Vova. Katya.)." Speech exercises result in the use of two-word sentences words. Speech therapist: "What are you doing?" Child: "Dragging the fox." Complication of the syntactic scheme of these sentences is carried out through the inclusion of secondary members of the sentence. It is important to remember the need to automate the same type of endings of nouns: first -y, then -a, later -o (nouns of the 2nd declension, middle genus.). In order to develop the skill of using grammatical forms, it is necessary to repeated pronunciation of endings (from 600 to 2,000 times). The repertoire of lexical units gradually expands. If at the beginning of work, preference is given to productive linguistic units, but later it is possible to introduce non-productive ones into the pupil's speech: the root morpheme and the sound and syllable content of words change. Words consisting of syllables with consonantal sounds (mny) are used less often than open (cata) and covered-closed (vagon) syllables (vagun) syllables. Words consisting of three syllables (boom gu) are used less often than two-syllable words (kita). When the child has learnt to confidently to use the masculine and feminine endings of nouns, it is possible to move on to their regular differentiation. In the process of differentiation practiced words are offered in free sequence:

- Who are you holding?
- Cata. Owl. Fox. Hedgehog. Goat. Horse.
Donkey. Sheep. Kita.

The content of speech therapy includes not only the grammatical and lexical subsystems, but also the phonetic structure of the language. The speech therapist constantly pays attention to the pronunciation of suffixes, endings of verbs and nouns. The child already uses the suffix verb suffix -i (Go! Run! Carry!). The most frequently verb endings are -y and -a. So, in pronunciation, we need to practice these are the vowel sounds: [i], [u], [a]. You can use articulation exercises "Fence", "Tube", "Fence- A.M. Gorchakova, E.A. Chaladze 30 Volga Pedagogical Bulletin. Tubochka", "Window", "Window opens - window closes" for active stimulation of sound

pronunciation, since it is these articulation exercises are included in the universal complex of articulation exercises. Let's look at the syllabic the syllabic structure of the words used at this stage he word is made up of two syllables. The word consists of two open syllables with stress on the second syllable. So, in the process of working on the syllabic structure of the word, the following rhythmic pattern should be practiced: tá - tá (- /) and tá - tá (/ - -). Thus, speech therapy work is carried out in unity over all the language subsystems: grammatical, lexical and phonetic. Let us dwell on the tasks of the third sub-stage of work:

1. To teach to use in independent expressive speech a two-jointed widespread sentence of three, four, five words (subject + predicate + object).object).

2. Teach to use in independent expressive speech the verb of the indicative mood, present tense, singular, 3rd person.

3. To teach to use in independent expressive speech an animate/inanimate noun of the 1st declension in the singular.1 declension in the singular, nominative case.

4. Teach to use in independent expressive speech an animate/inanimate noun of 1 declension in the singular, nominative case. 1 declension in the singular, genitive, dative, nominative and prepositional cases. et's take a closer look at the content of the third sub-stage. Corrective and speech therapy work is based on the sentences worked out earlier. The centre of the sentences become the main members: the predicate, expressed by the verb in the form of the 3rd person, singular, present tense; the subject, expressed by the animate noun of the 1st declension singular, nominative case. In the course of specially organized subject-practical activity of the child is a conversation. On the question of the speech therapist about what this or that person does, the child gives an answer. The child must use in the answer is already common two-jointed sentence of three to five words. When answering, attention is paid to the correct pronunciation of endings (stressed).In addition to questions about the actions of some persons, the speech therapist also asks questions about the persons themselves and about the persons who perform the actions: "Who is walking (carrying, sitting, etc.)?". Thus, several types of questions:

- What is someone doing? What is Dad (Mum, Vanya, Anya)?
- Who is doing something? Who is walking (carrying, sit, etc.)?
- Vanya is carrying who (what)?
- Who is carrying sový?

Materialized or graphic reference signal schemes are used. The speech therapist (and later child) pronounces a word and at the same time designates this word with a conventional graphic signal. All words are laid out in a linear sequence, corresponding to the order of pronunciation of words in a sentence. The speech therapist constantly pays attention to the pronunciation of suffixes, endings of verbs and nouns, thus mastering phonetic structure of the language. The child already uses the suffix -i of the verb, the most frequent endings -ý, -á. In the process of working on the pronunciation of verb endings, they move on to working out the sound combinations -it, -ot(-et). Actively put the sounds [o] and [t]. You can use articulation exercises "Drummer", "Automaton" to actively stimulation of sound pronunciation. Good result gives the technique of building up the base word by adding the sound [t] to a worked-out word: a verb in the form of the imperative mood, singular, 2nd person + the sound [t], e.g. sit + the sound [t] = sits, lay [t] = sits, lie - lies, dust - dusts, shout - shoutsIn this way, the sound content of words gradually becomes more complex, and soot-...Overcoming expressive alalia in children at the initial stage of speech therapy work Volga Pedagogical Bulletin. The syllabic structure of a word: from words with one or two

open syllables from words with one or two open syllables to two-syllable words consisting of open, covered and closed syllables and even syllables with stems. syllables and even syllables with consonant sounds. In the process of working on the syllabic structure of words, rhythmic patterns continue to be worked out: ta – tá (- /) and tá - tá (/ -). The third sub-stage involves differentiating between 1st and 3rd person verb forms (go - go). The content of this work is illustrated table 2

Differentiation of 1st and 3rd person verb forms

Speech therapy questions

What are you doing?

What is Vanya doing?

Go. Coming.

Carrying. Carrying.

Sitting. Sit.

Run. Runý t. Speech communication should continue to be formed in the activity: the child talks about his own actions and the actions of another person. The verb forms learnt at the verb forms worked out at the differentiation stage can be included in the following sentence patterns: "I am going and Daddy is coming. I go and Vanya is coming. I am sitting and Daddy is walking. I am walking and Vanya is sitting." In addition to performing actions, it is possible to work with visual material. In this capacity you can use figures of people and animals, photographs and story pictures and story pictures. Further in remedial and speech therapy work we use exercises to consolidate the forms of the name singular noun, genitive case. For this purpose, a popular game of hide-and-seek "There is no who?" is used. For example: "No who?" "No sister. (No fox. Noowl. No daddy. No Masha[s])." Later automatise and differentiate the forms of singular nouns of other indirect cases (dative, creative, prepositional). The work adheres to the ontogenetic principle of "from non-prepositional constructions to prepositional ones". The syntactic structure of the sentence is gradually expanded. A system of speech exercises is proposed, which is based on the gradual transition from a simple non-spoken two-sentence sentence to a simple two-sentence sentence simple non-spread compound sentence to a widespread one. All grammatical models are learnt gradually by the child in a practical way. Children's mastery of these grammatical models ensures readiness for mastering various types of complex (with a conjunctive and subordinating) sentences conjunctions) sentences. The proposed stages of work on the child's mastering of the language system can be presented in the form of Table 3. Improvement of the skill of practical use of grammatical models takes place in the process of forming coherent speech models occurs in the process of formation of coherent speech, as well as in the process of subsequent mastering of the written form of speech at school. The proposed system of correctional work will allow the formation of a unified language system of a child with a speech impediment and the development of a written form of speech at school. with speech deficiency and will be used by him/her in the process of live natural communication.

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